

Multifunctional Composites with Modified Carbon Fibers for Lightning Strike Protection

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1. Introduction

Lightning Strike is one of the most unpredictable and destructive forces that on average, strikes a commercial aircraft at least once a year or equivalent to 1,000-3,000 flight hours. The lightning effect can minimize avionic equipment performances and lead to severe accidents and fatalities.

A metallic mesh surface layer is currently used as lightning strike protection (LSP) system, however, the risk of galvanic corrosion in contact with carbon fiber composites and weight additions are the major concerns. Therefore, highly conductive nanofillers, namely, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs), are embedded into carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites enhancing functional conductivities and mechanical properties designed to carry high current and heat from lightning. The principal aim of this investigation is to progress into a new generation of conductive CFRP composites that could lead to further improvements in functional conductivity and mechanical property offering an adequate capability in withstanding lightning as well as increasing the efficiency of aircraft.

2. Materials and Methods

CNTs have been grown on carbon fiber through CVD method at low temperature, followed by adding GNPs into epoxy. CFRP composites were then fabricated using wet lay-up process and autoclave curing with only the outermost plies being modified.

3. Numerical Model

Woven CFRP composites (T300B) with 16-ply Atmospheric Temperature = 25°C Thermal radiation Emissivity (ϵ) = 0.9

Top Surface
Thermal radiation

Side Surface
Electrical Potential ($E = 0V$)
Thermal radiation

$$\text{Decomposition Index (DI)} = \begin{cases} 0 & T < 300^\circ\text{C} \\ \frac{T-300^\circ\text{C}}{510^\circ\text{C}-300^\circ\text{C}} & 300^\circ\text{C} \leq T \leq 510^\circ\text{C} \\ 1 & T > 510^\circ\text{C} \end{cases}$$

4. Results and Discussions

Morphology of CNTs on carbon fiber

Raman spectra analysis and thermogravimetric analysis

Type of specimens	CF	FF	0.05G/FF	0.1G/FF	0.2G/FF
CNTs	X	✓	✓	✓	✓
Content of GNP fillers (wt%)	0	0	0.05	0.1	0.2

Functional properties

Numerical damage area prediction in the CFRP composites

Electrical potential at 40 µs

Temperature profile in the thickness direction

Fuzzy fiber (FF) composites

0.1G/FF composites

5. Conclusions

A noticeable effect of growing CNTs on carbon fiber cloth has substantially enhanced both surface and through-thickness functional properties of CFRP composite. The synergistic physical interactions between GNPs and CNTs has led to further enhancement by creating varied phonon transport chains and electron transfer conductive percolation pathways between fibers. A numerical model was then developed to predict damage size (damage area, damage depth, maximum damage depth, and resin decomposition area) and temperature profile of composites with and without LSP layer under simulated lightning current. The inclusion of GNPs together with CNTs creates a possibility of developing conductive composites with increased functional and mechanical properties, opening an alternative to lightning strike protection (LSP) applications and opens up new opportunities for innovation and industrial applications.